

Performance evaluation of cryogenically treated tungsten carbide tool in milling operation on OHNS material

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Abstract

Improvement in wear resistance and hardness of cutting tool material is one of the most important challenges in machining operation. This issue can be overcome by improving the wear resistance and hardness by cryogenic treatment of tungsten carbide. In this work it is tried to study the effect of different soaking periods in cryogenic treatment of tungsten carbide. The experiments were conducted at temperature of 88K at different soaking periods of 8hrs, 20hrs, 24hrs and 30hrs, on commercially used tungsten carbide. Further efforts were made to quantify and confirm the effect of different soaking period along with the mechanism responsible for change in the hardness and wear resistance by measuring Rockwell hardness and weight loss during wear test.

The obtained result shows that there is a significant decrease in weight loss of 8hr soaked sample out of different soaking periods but, there was no change in bulk hardness. The weight loss during sliding wear test indicates the cryogenically treated tungsten carbide is more wear resistance due to increase in population density of carbides. Microstructure analysis of worn surface reflects the mechanism behind the improvement of mechanical properties.

Keywords: Cryogenic treatment, Soaking period, Tungsten carbide, Tool life.

1. Introduction

The cryogenic treatment of steels is to expose the material to sub-zero temperatures so as to impart or enhance the properties of the material. The literature describes the heat treatments mainly cryogenic treatments done on various types of tool steels. The Sequence of different heat treatment cycles followed by deep cryogenic treatment (DCT). The research conducted by a number of authors explains the effect of DCT on various material properties such as wear resistance, hardness, toughness and fatigue resistance, corrosion resistance in some cases. The mechanism of DCT has also been explained in later sections.

M. Prabhakaran, D. Madan, C. Sivakandhan, K. Anandan, S. Marichamy:

The cryogenic treatment was played an essential role in fabrication of products with high quality and improved substance properties. The present experimental work has to improve the substance properties of Oil Hardened Non Shrinkage (OHNS) steel. Through conventional treatment, there was no possibility to increase the substance properties of steel. In cryogenic treatment process, the OHNS steel was processed under $-190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The desired optimal factors were achieved through taguchi method. The role of factor and its effect has been studied through variance test. The different ranges of hardness were obtained after cryogenic treatment (57–65 HRC). The maximum hardness was achieved at the cooling rate of $6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, flow rate of 3 m/s and holding time of 30 h. The minimum wear rate was obtained at $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, flow rate of 1 m/s and holding time of 38 h. The wear rate was varied from 0.102–0.342 mm³/min. Through variance test, the flow rate of nitrogen was the most powerful factor on hardness (71.94%) and wear rate (32.65%).

Abdullah Sert, Osman Nuri Celik:

In recent years, the mechanism of cryogenic treatment to improve the mechanical properties of materials has become a subject of interest. In this study, the effect of shallow and deep cryogenic treatment on the micro structural and crystal structure of tungsten carbide (WC-Co) cutting tool material is investigated with the treatment mechanism being explained. As a result, the shallow and deep cryogenic treatment of WC-Co material did not cause any change in microstructure after high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM) investigations.

However, the binder Co element in its structure was determined to have martensitic transformation (α -Co (fcc) to ϵ -Co (hcp)) by the X-ray diffraction (XRD) method. It was determined in a Rietveld analysis that the ϵ -Co ratio is higher in deep cryogenic treatment than in shallow cryogenic treatment and the untreated sample. In addition it was determined that tempering after the cryogenic treatment decreases the amount of Martensitic transformation.

In this study, no significant endothermic peak formation is observed in the tungsten carbide samples around $420\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the TGA analysis, there is no structural deterioration due to an increase in temperature.

S.T.Dhande, V.A.Kane, M.M.Dhobe, C.L.Gogte:

Improvement in wear resistance and hardness of cutting tool material is one of the most important challenges in machining operation. In this work it is tried to study the effect of different soaking periods in cryogenic treatment of tungsten carbide. The experiments were conducted at temperature of 88K at different soaking periods of 8hrs, 16hrs, 24hrs and 30hrs on commercially used tungsten carbide. Further efforts were made to quantify and confirm the effect of different soaking period along with the mechanism responsible for change in the hardness and wear resistance by measuring Rockwell hardness and weight loss during wear test. CT shows significant reduction in weight loss of WC-Co tool at 8hr soaking period by 67%. There is a reduction in cobalt percentage in β phase of matrix of WC-Co after the (CT1) by 53%. Cobalt content reduction results in formation of η phase on the surface of the treated sample.

Relative intensity of η carbide increased from insignificant in UT sample to significant in treated (CT1-8hr soaking period) sample.

The average diameter of α phase and η phase particles is 9.5031nm and 13.1922 nm in the untreated sample after the CT it is observed to be 5.1333nm and 4.922nm respectively. Improvement in the wear characteristics is also

observed due to refinement of the structure, formation of stable structure and proper alignment of particles

B.N. Sahoo , A. Mohanty , S. Gangopadhyay , Vipindas K:

Cryogenic treatment is one of the potential techniques to enhance cutting tool performance. The present work investigates the microstructure and machining performance of cemented carbide (WC-Co) inserts through deep cryogenic treatment. For this, ISO P30 WC-Co inserts were exposed to deep cryogenic treatment (-196 °C), accompanied by tempering at 200 °C.

Machining operation was carried out by considering three different cutting speeds (i.e. at 100, 150, and 200 m/min.) with constant feed rate and depth of cut of 0.2 mm/rev and 1 mm, respectively. After cryogenic treatment, significant improvement in the average flank wear and crater wear of WC-Co insert was observed. The cryogenic treatment increases the binder phase concentration, i. e. cobalt which enhanced the bonding strength, hence toughness of the WC particles in the carbide tool. 2 An increase in hardness of cryogenically treated tools was found but, the increment was a nominal 3%.

2. Methods and Experimental Setup

2.1 Cutting tool materials

The classes of cutting tool materials currently in use for machining operation are high speed tool steel, cobalt-base alloys, cemented carbides, ceramic, and polycrystalline cubic boron nitride and polycrystalline diamond. The Ideal cutting tool material should have all of the following characteristics:

- Harder than the work it is cutting
- High temperature stability
- Resists wear and thermal shock
- Impact resistant
- Chemically inert to the work material and cutting fluid

To effectively select tools for machining, a machinist or engineer must have specific Information about:

- The starting and finished part shape
- The work piece hardness
- The material's tensile strength
- The material's abrasiveness
- The type of chip generated
- The work holding setup
- The power and speed capacity of the machine tool
- Some common cutting tool materials are described below:

1. Carbon steels:

Carbon steels have been used since the 1880s for cutting tools. However carbon steels start to soften at a temperature of about 180°C. This limitation means that such tools are rarely used for metal cutting operations. Plain carbon steel tools, containing about 0.9% carbon and about 1% manganese, hardened to about 62 Rc, are widely used for wood working and they can be used in a router to machine aluminium sheet up to about 3mm thick.

2. High speed steels (HSS):

HSS tools are so named because they were developed to cut at higher speeds. Developed around 1900 HSS are the most highly alloyed tool steels. The tungsten (T series) was developed first and typically contains 12 - 18% tungsten, plus about 4% chromium and 17- 5% vanadium. Most grades contain about 0.5% molybdenum and most grades contain 4- 12% cobalt. It was soon discovered that molybdenum (smaller proportions) could be substituted for most of the tungsten resulting in a more economical formulation which had better abrasion resistance than the T series and undergoes less distortion during heat treatment. Consequently about 95% of all HSS tools are made from M series grades. These contain 5 - 10% molybdenum, 1.5 - 10% tungsten, 1 - 4% vanadium, 4% Chromium and many grades contain 5 - 10% cobalt.

HSS tools are tough and suitable for interrupted cutting and are used to manufacture tools of complex shape such as drills, reamers, taps, dies and gear cutters. Tools may also be coated to improve wear resistance. HSS accounts for the largest tonnage of tool materials currently used. Typical cutting speeds: 10 - 60 m/min.

3. Cast Cobalt alloys:

Introduced in early 1900s these alloys have compositions of about 40 - 55% cobalt, 30% chromium and 10 - 20% tungsten and are not heat treatable. Maximum hardness values of 55 - 64 Rc. They have good wear resistance but are not as tough as HSS but can be used at somewhat higher speeds than HSS. Now only in limited use.

4. Carbides:

Also known as cemented carbides or sintered carbides were introduced in the 1930s and have high hardness over a wide range of temperatures, high thermal conductivity, high Young's modulus making them effective tool and die materials for a range of applications. The two groups used for machining are tungsten carbide and titanium carbide; both types may be coated or uncoated. Tungsten carbide particles (1 to 5 Micrometers) are bonded together in a cobalt matrix using powder metallurgy. The powder is pressed and sintered to the required insert shape. Titanium and niobium carbides may also be included to impart special properties. A wide range of grades are available for different applications. Sintered carbide tips are the dominant type of material used in metal cutting. The proportion of cobalt (the usual matrix material) present has a significant effect on the properties of carbide tools. 3 - 6% matrix of cobalt gives greater hardness while 6 - 15% matrix of cobalt gives a

greater toughness while decreasing the hardness, wear resistance and strength. Tungsten carbide tools are commonly used for machining steels, cast irons and abrasive non-ferrous materials. Titanium carbide has a higher wear resistance than tungsten but is not as tough. With a nickel-molybdenum alloy as the matrix, TiC is suitable for machining at higher speeds than those which can be used for tungsten carbide. Typical cutting speeds are: 30 - 150 m/min or 100 - 250 when coated.

5. Coatings

Coatings are frequently applied to carbide tool tips to improve tool life or to enable higher cutting speeds. Coated tips typically have lives 10 times greater than uncoated tips. Common coating materials include titanium nitride, titanium carbide and aluminium oxide, usually 2 - 15 micro-m thick. Often several different layers may be applied, one on top of another, depending upon the intended application of the tip. The techniques used for applying coatings include chemical vapor deposition (CVD) plasma assisted CVD and physical vapor deposition (PVD). Diamond coatings are also in use and being further developed.

2.2 Types of Coating method:

- 1) PVD (Physical Vapour Deposition)
- 2) CVD (Chemical Vapour Deposition)

1) PVD (Physical Vapour Deposition)

Refers to a variety of thin film deposition techniques where solid metal is vaporized in a high vacuum environment and deposited on electrically conductive materials as a pure metal or alloy coating. As a process that transfers the coating material on a single atom or molecule level, it can provide extremely pure and high performance coatings which for many applications are much preferable to electroplating. PVD Coating processes are environmentally friendly processes that can greatly reduce the amount of toxic substances that must be disposed of with more conventional types of coating that involve fluid precursors and chemical reactions.

At the heart of every microchip and semiconductor device, PVD Coatings enable the solar panel industry to make greener electricity as well as surgical and medical implants that require the highest degrees of purity. It produces coatings with superior hardness, durability and resistance to wear. PVD Coatings reduce friction for high performance moving parts making them widely used in the aerospace and automotive industry, and for cutting tools where long lasting durability is the crucial success factor.

PVD is fundamentally a vacuum coating technique vaporizing a metal to plasma of atoms or molecules and depositing them on a wide range of substrates. Carried out in a high vacuum chamber approximating outer space at 10^{-2} to 10^{-4} milli bar, the process usually takes place between 150 and 500° C. Additionally, reactive gasses such as nitrogen, oxygen or acetylene are introduced into the vacuum deposition chamber to produce a very strong bond between the coating and substrate when it's deposited. Although the thin film coatings are only a few microns thick, they form an extremely adherent coating with high lubricity lowering friction and heat that makes PVD the perfect choice for high performance cutting tools and engine parts.

2) CVD (*chemical vapor deposition*)

Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD) is an atmosphere controlled process conducted at elevated temperatures ($\sim 1925^{\circ}$ F) in a CVD reactor. During this process, thin-film coatings are formed as the result of reactions between various gaseous phases and the heated surface of substrates within the CVD reactor. As different gases are transported through the reactor, distinct coating layers are formed on the tooling substrate. For example, TiN is formed as a result of the following chemical reaction: $\text{TiCl}_4 + \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{1000^{\circ}\text{C}} \text{TiN} + 4\text{HCl} + \text{H}_2$. Titanium carbide (TiC) is formed as the result of the following chemical reaction: $\text{TiCl}_4 + \text{CH}_4 + \text{H}_2 \xrightarrow{1030^{\circ}\text{C}} \text{TiC} + 4\text{HCl} + \text{H}_2$. The final product of these reactions is a hard, wear-resistant coating that exhibits a chemical and metallurgical bond to the substrate.

CVD coatings are used in many manufacturing applications as a wear-resistant coating: carbide milling and turning inserts, wear components, some plastic processing tools, etc. However, the most common application for CVD coating is for metal-forming tools. CVD coatings provide excellent resistance to the types of wear and galling typically seen during many metal-forming applications.

In high stress metal-forming applications, where the tool's tolerances and substrate permit, high temperature CVD coating processes will perform better than "cold" processes like PVD, thin-dense chrome (TDC), nitriding, etc. The chemical/metallurgical bonding that results from the CVD coating process creates adhesion characteristics that simply cannot be duplicated by a "cold" process. This enhanced adhesion protects forming tools from the sliding friction wear-out caused by the severe shearing stresses generated in heavy metal-forming applications.

2.3 Types of Coating Material

1. Cermets:

Developed in the 1960s, these typically contain 70% aluminium oxide and 30% titanium carbide. Some formulation contains molybdenum carbide, niobium carbide and tantalum carbide. Their

performance is between those of carbides and ceramics and coatings seem to offer few benefits. Typical cutting speeds: 150 - 350 m/min.

2. Alumina:

Introduced in the early 1950s, two classes are used for cutting tools: fine grained high purity aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) and silicon nitride (Si_3N_4) are pressed into insert tip shapes and sintered at high temperatures. Additions of titanium carbide and zirconium Oxide (ZrO_2) may be made to improve properties. But while ZrO_2 improves the fracture toughness, it reduces the hardness and thermal conductivity. Silicon carbide (SiC) whiskers may be added to give better toughness and improved thermal shock resistance. The tips have high abrasion resistance and hot hardness and their superior chemical stability compared to HSS and carbides means they are less likely to adhere to the metals during cutting and consequently have a lower tendency to form a built up edge. Their main weakness is low toughness and negative rake angles are often used to avoid chipping due to their low tensile strengths. Stiff machine tools and work set ups should be used when machining with ceramic tips as otherwise vibration is likely to lead to premature failure of the tip. Typical cutting speeds: 150-650 m/min.

3. Silicon Nitride:

In the 1970s a tool material based on silicon nitride was developed, these may also contain aluminium oxide, yttrium oxide and titanium carbide. SiN has an affinity for iron and is not suitable for machining steels. A specific type is 'Sialon', containing the elements: silicon, aluminium, oxygen and nitrogen. This has higher thermal shock resistance than silicon nitride and is recommended for machining cast irons and nickel based super alloys at intermediate cutting speeds.

4. Cubic Boron Nitride (CBN):

Introduced in the early 1960s, this is the second hardest material available after diamond CBN tools may be used either in the form of small solid tips or as a 0.5 to 1 mm thick layer of polycrystalline boron nitride sintered onto a carbide substrate under pressure. In the latter case the carbide provides shock resistance and the CBN layer provides very high wear resistance and cutting edge strength. Cubic boron nitride is the standard choice for machining alloy and tool steels with a hardness of 50 Rc or higher. Typical cutting speeds: 30 - 310 m/min.

5. Diamond:

The hardest known substance is diamond. Although single crystal diamond has been used as a tool, they are brittle and need to be mounted at the correct crystal orientation to obtain optimal tool life. Single crystal diamond tools have been mainly replaced by polycrystalline diamond (PCD). This

consists of very small synthetic crystals fused by a high temperature high pressure process to a thickness of between 0.5 and 1mm and bonded to a carbide substrate. The result is similar to CBN tools. The random orientation of the diamond crystals prevents the propagation of cracks, improving toughness. Because of its reactivity, PCD is not suitable for machining plain carbon steels or nickel, titanium and cobalt based alloys. PCD is most suited to light uninterrupted finishing cuts at almost any speed and is mainly used for very high speed machining of aluminium -silicon alloys, composites and other non - metallic materials. Typical cutting speeds: 200- 2000 m/min.

As rates of metal removal have increased, so has the need for heat resistant cutting tools. The result has been a progression from high-speed steels to carbide, and on to ceramics and other super hard materials. High-speed steels cut four times faster than the carbon steels they replaced. There are over 30 grades of high-speed steel, in three main categories: tungsten, molybdenum, and molybdenum-cobalt based grades. In industry today, carbide tools have replaced high-speed steels in most applications. These carbide and coated carbide tools cut about 3 to 5 times faster than high-speed steels. Cemented carbide is a powder metal product consisting of fine carbide particles cemented together with a binder of cobalt. The major categories of hard carbide include tungsten carbide, titanium carbide, tantalum carbide, and niobium carbide.

Ceramic cutting tools are harder and more heat-resistant than carbides, but more brittle. They are well suited for machining cast iron, hard steels, and the super alloys. Two types of ceramic cutting tools are available: the alumina-based and the silicon nitride-based ceramics. The alumina-based ceramics are used for high speed semi- and final-finishing of ferrous and some non-ferrous materials. The silicon nitride-based ceramics are generally used for rougher and heavier machining of cast iron and the super alloys.

2.4 CRYOGENIC TREATMENT

1. Introduction

Cryogenics is defined as the branches of physics and engineering that study very low temperatures, how to produce them, and how materials behave at those temperatures. The word Cryogenics is derived from the Greek words “Kryos” (meaning cold) and “Genes” (meaning born). The word cryogenics literally means "the production of icy cold".

2. Cryogenic Processing

The cryogenic processing is modification of a material or component using cryogenic temperatures. The workers at the National Institute of Standards and Technology at Boulder, Colorado have chosen to consider the field of cryogenics as that involving temperatures below -180°C (93.15 K). Cryogenic

processing makes changes to the crystal structure of materials. Deep sub-zero (much below 0C) processing of metals and alloys is a deep stress relieving technology. The third law of thermodynamics states that entropy is zero at absolute zero temperature. Cryogenic processing uses this principle to relieve stresses in the material. The materials are subjected to extremely low temperatures for long period of time leading to development of equilibrium. This leads to decrease in defects in the material and it attains a minimum entropy state.

Cryogenic processing will not in itself harden metal like quenching and tempering. It is not a substitute for heat-treating. It is an addition to heat-treating. Most alloys will not show much of a change in hardness due to cryogenic processing. The material will have to be cryogenically treated followed by tempering to gain the hardness and toughness.

3. Classification of Cryogenic Treatment

Cryogenic treatment has been classified into shallow cryogenic treatment (SCT) and deep cryogenic treatment (DCT) depending upon the temperatures in which the material is treated:

- 1) SCT- tool steel is keep in freezer at 193K for 5 h and then exposed to RT
- 2) DCT- material is brought down to 77K at 1.26 K/min, held there for 24 h and brought back to RT at 0.63 K/min.

Figure a: Variations of temperatures during Cryogenic Treatment

The used carbide cutting tools at two different rates of cooling/heating (0.5 °C/min and 1 °C/min) and completed the cryo-treatment in 8h and 4h and reported that the wear resistance was better in the sample (0.5 °C/min,8h) compared to (1 °C/min,4h).sudden decrease in temperature (thermal shock) reduces the cost of cryo treatment but increases the risk of occurrence of micro cracks in the microstructure of the specimen due to which the specimen may not give better performance.

Figure b: Cryogenic treatment arrangement

2.5 Modified Cryogenic system

The cryogenic equipment is shown in figure 3.4. It consists of an insulated box in which material can be kept. One circulating fan is used to circulate the gases. A thermocouple is used to measure the temperature. This whole system is controlled by computer system. Tank containing liquid nitrogen is attached to this box through solenoid valve.

Fig.c: Advance Cryo-processor (vaporized liquid phase)

2.5.1. Parameters of cryogenic treatment

These parameters are cooling rate, soaking temperature, soaking period and warming rate. These parameters also have contribution in improvement in wear characteristics.

A] Cooling rate and warming rate

Cooling rate is the rate at which the sample is slowly cooled down to soaking temperature. Warming rate is the rate at which sample is warmed slowly up to room temperature. It was observed that the slow cooling and warming rate of about 1-3 K/min were used to avoid the thermal micro cracking of material.

B] Soaking temperature

Soaking temperature is temperature at which sample is held for given soaking period. First users of CT applied the soaking temperature in the range 193 to 173 K. Now the recent application which is known as deep CT uses the temperature in the range 103 K to 77 K.

C] Soaking period

Soaking period is that period at which sample is held at low temperature. From previous studies it was found that soaking period vary from 8hr to 40 hr. Das found in his work that from the different soaking period 36hr soaking period gives the better resistance properties to AISI D2 steel.

WC-Co insert generally have cobalt binder. Cobalt is present next to iron in periodic Table. Cobalt has same valance electron and forms same crystal structure as the iron. The iron and cobalt both are affected by the CT and has contribution in the enhancement of hardness. Hence it was stipulated that WC-Co which contains cobalt shows similar response to CT as that of the steels.

Many researches had studied the effect of CT on WC-Co tools and found interesting results like improvement in tools life improvement in mechanical properties etc.

2.5.2. Tempering Process:

Tempering is usually done after the cryogenic treatment. The process is mainly performed to remove the internal stresses of the specimen that occur due to excessive cooling in cryogenic treatment. Generally, the process is applied to cutting tools by holding the specimen at 150–200 °C for 1.5–2 h. In some previous studies has under gone double tempering after cryogenic treatment and a fine distribution of Carbide particles have been obtained by double Tempering after CT8.

In some studied the results show that Tempering indeed maximizes the gain in tool life after DCT (86% without Tempering, 126% with Tempering). Through investigations have found that tempering before actually decreases wear resistance as against increasing it. On a hind note it has been observed that multiple cycles of Tempering after DCT hasn't improved on the wear resistance, but has a negative impact. Also there has been decrease in wear resistance after multiple cycles of Tempering, compared to CT and HCT samples.

Fig.: Tempering process setup

2.6.SELLECTION OF RAW MATERIALS

A] Need for Research

From the detailed literature review it is identified that OHNS steel is missing. This OHNS is mostly used in the die manufacturing industries and power transmitting elements. So, this OHNS material is selected as a working material.

B] OHNS (OIL HARDENED NON SHRINKAGE STEEL)

The material used for this work is OHNS steel. OHNS steel is a general purpose tool steel that is typically used in applications where alloy steels cannot provide sufficient hardness, strength and wear resistance.

Chemical composition of OHNS material

Sr. No.	Element name	Composition (%)
1	Carbon (C)	0.96
2	Manganese (Mn)	1.36
3	Chromium (Cr)	0.51
4	Nickel (Ni)	0.10
5	Molybdenum (Mo)	0.06
6	Tungsten (W)	0.45
7	Sulfur (S)	0.017
8	Phosphorus (P)	0.020
9	Silicon (Si)	0.32

Table2.6

From the metallurgical testing, the hardness of OHNS material is in the range of 91-92 HRB. This material are used to making a die.

The hardening temperature of OHNS steel is between 7900 C and 8200 C. OHNS steel is a non - shrinkage steel. This term refers to steels which show little change in volume from the annealed state when hardened and tempered at low temperatures. Such steels are required to master tools, gauges and dies which must not change size when hardened after machining in the annealed condition.

2.6.1. Mechanical Properties of OHNS Steel

- I. **Strength and Hardness:** Generally the strength increases as the carbon and manganese content increases. Given the high percentage of both of those, OHNS becomes strong. OHNS has 58 RC to 64 RC hardness
- II. **Toughness and Brittleness:** Toughness of a material determines whether it can be subjected to shock conditions, and the extent to which it may undergo deformity in shape but still not snap. OHNS steel tends to be very tough. As opposed to toughness, brittleness measures whether a material will snap instead of getting deformed, when load is applied. OHNS steels are less brittle than cast or pig iron because of the presence of magnesium.
- III. **Ductility and Malleability:** Ductility is a material's ability to be drawn into wires without breaking. Ductility decreases with increasing carbon, and because OHNS steel has very high carbon content, it is not

very ductile. On the other hand, malleability determines a material's ability to be rolled into sheets without getting ruptured. OHNS steel is quite malleable and can be worked upon even at low room temperatures.

2.6.2. Applications of OHNS Steel

It is to be considered as die steel. It is used for manufacturing of blanking and stamping dies, rotary shear blades, thread outting tools, milling cutters, measuring tools, gauging tools, wood working tools, reamers, etc.

Fig.e : OHNS Material Sample

2.7. SELECTION OF RAW MATERIALS

We are selected the cutting tool material as tungsten carbide from research paper. This insert is coated type insert. The coating on insert is Titanium aluminide(TiAl). There is no one done the experiment TiAl insert on die material as OHNS material.

Grade of insert: APMT1135PDER-T

Coating method: PVD

Fig.f: Coated Tungsten carbide cutting tool insert

2.7.1. Tungsten carbide

Tungsten carbide (WC-Co) is extensively used as cutting tool material. It has different types of tool grades with different hardness. Different grade are used for the different material. WC-Co is a composite which contain the Tungsten, Cobalt (6%), Titanium and Niobium. WC-Co is the product of powder metallurgy in which the powder of tungsten carbide is mixed with the cobalt binder. This mixture goes through blending, compacting and sintering process to get the final product. WC-Co is refractory material. It has high hardness and wears resistance.

2.7.2. Manufacturing process of WC-Co tools

Powder metallurgy technique was used by Schroeter in 1923 for obtaining the fully consolidated product of tungsten carbide.

- I. Schroeter blended fine WC powder with a small amount of Iron, Nickel, or Cobalt powder.
- II. This blended mixture was pressed and compacted under high pressure.
- I. Finally compacted mixture was sintered at approximately 1573^0 K.
- II. This WC-Co material is used in a wide range of applications, including metal cutting, mining, construction, rock drilling, metal forming, structural components, and wear parts. Approximately 50% of all carbide production is used for metal cutting applications.

2.7.3 Important properties of Tungsten Carbide

Tungsten Carbide-Cobalt alloys are commonly referred as straight grades. These alloys have excellent resistance to simple abrasive wear and thus have many applications in metal cutting operations. The microstructures of WC-Co alloys contain the phases as given below

1. Angular WC grains and
2. η Phase (Shaded gray phase)

Fig. g: Micro structure of WC-Co material

Above figure shows the η Phase ($\text{Co}_6\text{W}_6\text{C}$) which appears as shaded gray with clearly defined grain boundaries. Bright phase WC particles are surrounded by η phase because of the solubility of WC-Co in the binder. Due to insufficient amount of carbon in WC-Co material during manufacturing there is formation of a series of double carbides ($\text{Co}_3\text{W}_3\text{C}$ or $\text{Co}_6\text{W}_6\text{C}$).

This new formed group is commonly known as η phase. The formation of η phase involves the dissolution of the original carbides into the cobalt binder. Eta (η) phase appears as gray phase in microstructure

2.7.4 Tool Life

Tool life generally indicates the amount of satisfactory performance given by a cutting tool till it is declared to fail. Various studies define the tool life in different way tool life is always expressed by span of machining period in minutes, whereas in industries besides machining time in minutes some other means are also used to assess tool life, depending upon the situation, such as

- I. Number of pieces of work machined

- II. Total volume of material removed
- III. Total length of cut.

2.8. Milling Machine and Milling Operation

We are used vertical milling machine for machining. The milling operation selected for trial is rough or plunge milling operation. In the milling operation the material removal rate is more required for die manufacturing. Plunge milling is very good method for rough machining process of complex shape. It is also called as z-axis milling.

Advantage of CNC plunge milling over conventional milling

- I. The radial cutting forces, which is responsible for the deformation of the tool and the work piece, is very small.
- II. The material which is difficult to cut can be rough machined easily.
- III. The vibration can be avoided in the machine so that is suitable for deep cavity machining like mould and cavity making.

Fig. h : VMC Machine

2.9. Weight Measurement

MRR is the rate at which the material is removed from the work piece. Turning operation takes place between the tool and the work piece during the machining process material is removed. The MRR is

defined as the ratio of the difference in weight of the work piece before and after machining to the machining time.

Fig. i : Weight measuring machine

2.10. Surface Roughness Measurement

Roughness measurement has been done using a portable surface roughness tester, SURFTEST (Mitutoyo).

The surface roughness values like Ra, measured using surface roughness tester with model no. SJ 210 178-561-01A for measurement. The detector with instrument is 0.75 mN type with stylus tip radius 2 μm with measuring force 0.75 mN. Surface roughness measurement has been shown in Figure

Fig. j: Surface Tester

3. Result and Discussion

3.1. Selection of Parameters and Levels

3.1.1. OVAT (one variable at a time) analysis

OVAT analysis is very much important tool utilized widely in engineering analysis. A control factors and there levels are selected for experimentation by using OVAT analysis. The main purpose of performing OVAT analysis is to clear that whether the selected process parameters having influence on quality characteristic. OVAT analysis perform by varying one process parameter from lower to higher value by keeping all other process parameter constant, and measure the effect on quality characteristic. Before going to the main experimentation, some discussion with company peoples and with the help of research paper was selected three input parameter like speed, feed, and depth of cut.

From the basis of research paper, experience and catalogue, we are select the three different range of speed, feed and depth of cut.

Speed range: (1000-4000) rpm

Feed range: (0.1-0.8) mm/rev

Depth of cut range: (0.1-0.8) mm

3.1.1.1. Speed

The level of speed in between 1000-4000 rpm selected. Speed changing and remaining parameter feed, depth of cut are constant and result surface roughness are taken and Generally, when speed increases the Ra value decreases but in this condition Ra value does not decreases. It is shown in table. Because the depth of cut and feed are maximum as per condition. But in this table shows when speed increases the material removal rate increases.

Sr.No	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	DOC(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	1375	0.8	0.8	28.16	1.274
2	1750	0.8	0.8	35.84	1.133
3	2125	0.8	0.8	42.4	2.207

4	2520	0.8	0.8	51.7	1.534
5	2875	0.8	0.8	58.88	1.389
6	3250	0.8	0.8	66.56	1.189
7	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.31
8	4000	0.8	0.8	81.92	1.584

Table no. 3.1.1.1:- OVAT analysis of Speed

a) Graphical analysis

Graph no: a) Speed vs MRR

Graph no: b) speed vs. Ra value

The variation in MRR and Ra value are shown in above graph. When maximum speed then the MRR is maximum. Ra value vary with respect to speed variation is shown in graph.

3.1.1.2. Depth of cut

The levels of depth of cut 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, are selected. Depth of cut changing and remaining parameter speed, feed are same and result surface roughness are taken and from table it is clear that as depth of cut increases the surface roughness increases. Hence depth of cut is influencing factor on surface roughness.

sr.no	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	DOC(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra
1	4000	0.8	0.1	10.24	1.058
2	4000	0.8	0.2	20.48	1.126
3	4000	0.8	0.3	30.72	1.331
4	4000	0.8	0.4	40.96	1.174

5	4000	0.8	0.5	51.2	1.302
6	4000	0.8	0.6	61.44	1.126
7	4000	0.8	0.7	71.68	1.258
8	4000	0.8	0.8	81.92	0.969

Table no.3.2.1.2: OVAT analysis of depth of cut

The variation in MRR and Ra value with respect to depth of cut as shown in above graph. We are seen that when depth of cut is maximum the MRR also maximum and when depth cut is maximum then Ra value minimum.

3.1.1.3. Feed

The levels of Feed 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8 are selected. Feed changing and remaining parameter speed, depth of cut putting mean and result surface roughness are taken and from table it is clear that as feed increases the surface roughness increases. Hence feed is influencing factor on surface roughness.

Sr. No	Speed	Feed	DOC	MRR	Ra Value
1	4000	0.1	0.8	10.24	0.7
2	4000	0.2	0.8	20.48	0.712
3	4000	0.3	0.8	30.72	0.881
4	4000	0.4	0.8	40.96	1.179

5	4000	0.5	0.8	51.2	1.338
6	4000	0.6	0.8	61.44	1.484
7	4000	0.7	0.8	71.68	1.533
8	4000	0.8	0.8	81.92	1.133

Table no. 2.11.1.3 : OVAT analysis of feed

The variation in MRR and Ra value with respect to feed are shown in graph. In graph show at minimum feed the Ra value also minimum and at maximum feed the MRR is maximum.

3.2. Result from OVAT analysis

From the OVAT analysis we are found the different level of parameter. We are select optimum parameter of speed, feed and depth of cut.

The optimum level parameter is shown in table.

Sr.no	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	3250	0.6	0.6	66.56	1.189
2	3625	0.7	0.7	74.24	1.31
3	4000	0.8	0.8	81.92	1.13

Table no.3.2: Optimum parameter level

3.3. Taguchi Method

The Taguchi method involves reducing the variation in a process through robust design of experiments. The overall objective of the method is to produce high quality product at low cost to the manufacturer. The Taguchi method was developed by Dr. Genichi Taguchi of Japan who maintained that variation. Taguchi developed a method for designing experiments to investigate how different parameters affect the mean and variance of a process performance characteristic that defines how well the process is functioning. The experimental design proposed by Taguchi involves using orthogonal arrays to organize the parameters affecting the process and the levels at which they should be varies. Instead of having to test all possible combinations like the factorial design, the Taguchi method tests pairs of combinations. This allows for the collection of the necessary data to determine which factors most affect product quality with a minimum amount of experimentation, thus saving time and resources. The Taguchi method is best used when there is an intermediate number of a variable (3 to 50), few interactions between variables, and when only a few variables contribute significantly.

To take optimum level from OVAT analysis and to make a 27 array by using Mini Tab software.

3.3.1 27 array for Design of Experiment

Sr. No	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	3250	0.6	0.8	49.92	2.721
2	3250	0.6	0.8	49.92	1.2
3	3250	0.6	0.8	49.92	1.417

4	3250	0.7	0.7	50.96	1.299
5	3250	0.7	0.7	50.96	1.626
6	3250	0.7	0.7	50.96	1.418
7	3250	0.8	0.6	49.92	1.999
8	3250	0.8	0.6	49.92	3.085
9	3250	0.8	0.6	49.92	1.637
10	3625	0.6	0.7	48.72	2.201
11	3625	0.6	0.7	48.72	1.425
12	3625	0.6	0.7	48.72	1.679
13	3625	0.7	0.6	48.72	1.664
14	3625	0.7	0.6	48.72	1.291
15	3625	0.7	0.6	48.72	1.291
16	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.864
17	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.447
18	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.292
19	4000	0.6	0.6	46.08	0.642
20	4000	0.6	0.6	46.08	0.828
21	4000	0.6	0.6	46.08	1.406
22	4000	0.7	0.8	71.68	2.208
23	4000	0.7	0.8	71.68	1.085
24	4000	0.7	0.8	71.68	1.394
25	4000	0.8	0.7	71.68	2.049
26	4000	0.8	0.7	71.68	1.36
27	4000	0.8	0.7	71.68	0.966

Table no. 3.3.1 : 27 Array of DOE

We are focusing on maximum MRR. In this table we are seen that different mrr with corresponding level. From this table find maximum MRR reading and also corresponding Parameter

3.2.2 Result from taguchi method

The optimum level of parameter from DOE is followed

Sr. No	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.292

3.4 Rockwell Hardness test

Sample no.	Soaking period	1	2	3	Avg. Hardness(HRB)
1	4	25.5	26.5	26	26
2	12	21	26	26	24.33
3	20	26	27	26	26.33
4	28	24	24	25	24.33
UT	-	17	16	16	16

Table no. 3.4: Hardness test

3.5. Tool life analysis

We are observing the performance of both treated and untreated sample of cutting tool insert. The tool life is dependent upon wear resistance of material. From the machining of both untreated and treated cutting tool insert we can easily find out the wear of the tool. From this observation we can understand the better wear resistance cutting tool insert.

Type of sample	Soaking period(hrs)	Weight loss of insert in (gm)	% weight loss of insert
UT	-	0.170	-
CT	20	0.020	0.35

Table no.3.5: wear analysis

4. CONCLUSION

4.1 Conclusion from OVAT analysis

From the OVAT analysis we are found the different level of parameter. We are select optimum parameter of speed, feed and depth of cut.

The optimum level parameters are shown in table.

Sr.no	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	3250	0.6	0.6	66.56	1.189
2	3625	0.7	0.7	74.24	1.31
3	4000	0.8	0.8	81.92	1.13

4.2 Conclusion from taguchi method

The optimum level of parameter from DOE is followed

Sr. No	Speed(rpm)	Feed(mm/rev)	Depth of cut(mm)	MRR(mm ³ /min)	Ra value(um)
1	3625	0.8	0.8	74.24	1.292

4.3 Conclusion from tool life

Based on the results obtained in this study , following conclusions can be drawn regarding the effect of different soaking period on wear characteristic and the mechanism of change in the improvement of wear characteristics after the CT of tungsten carbide.

- I. Improvement in the wear characteristics is also observed due to refinement of the structure, formation of stable structure and proper alignment of particle.

Type of sample	Soaking period(hrs)	Weight loss of insert in (gm)	% weight loss of insert

UT	-	0.170	-
CT	20	0.020	0.35

5.4 Conclusion from hardness test

Sample Name	Soaking period	Avg. Hardness(HRB)
CT	20	26.33
UT	-	16

From the table we can see that

To increase in hardness of treated insert as compared to untreated insert.

I. Future Scope

Present work is based on the effect of cryogenic treatment on tool and process parameters like Speed, Feed and Depth of cut on Surface roughness and MRR. Future investigation leaves a wide scope for the researcher to study on the cryogenic treatment, Surface roughness and MRR during vertical milling operation CNC machine and to study on the phenomenon which we can improve tool with various of tool.

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